

Relationship between summation of daily difference between transpiration of control and stressed plants, and grain yield. IRRI, 1988.

line, differences in grain yield with drought at different growth stages can be entirely accounted for by differences in $S(T_c - T_s)$.

Though IR64 was most susceptible to yield reduction by drought at flowering, it was not most sensitive to water deficit then. Rather, stress developed fastest and plants were most severely stressed at flowering because rapid growth then used water fastest. It appears that $S(T_c - T_s)$ alone, with no factor to scale for growth stage, can be used as a drought stress index to compare results of screening trials in different locations and years. □

A low-cost rapid screening technique for seminal root elongation

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Deep roots offer resistance to drought. To identify deep-rooted rice genotypes, we developed a new method of growing seedlings in solution culture. This technique fosters seminal root growth in young seedlings by hindering adventitious root growth:

1. With nylon net, cover tightly the mouth of a tall measuring cylinder or

glass jar, preferably 30 cm high, 8 cm diameter (see figure).

2. Fill the jar to its brim with water.
3. Place 25 uniform pregerminated seeds over the nylon net so they touch the water.
4. Radicles enter the water in 24 h.
5. Daily, drain the water level to arrest adventitious root growth so only tips of long radicles touch the water by 1 mm. (To drain water from jar, use a small rubber tube 2 mm in diameter.) The seedlings with short or malformed radicles will dry up.
6. Thereafter, drain the water every 24 h, continuing to allow root tips to touch the water.
7. Seven days after germination, take out the seedlings and compare lengths of seminal roots. Deep-rooted genotypes will develop longer seminal roots.

The advantages of this technique follow:

1. Root elongation provides valid data for drought resistance.
2. Shallow-rooted genotypes vary

Pregerminated seeds grown for 1 wk in a tall glass cylinder, mouth covered with nylon net.

greatly from deep-rooted genotypes, allowing quick visual screening.

3. Where a greenhouse is not available, this simple technique can supplement field data. □

Excess water tolerance

Performance of rice breeding lines under medium deepwater conditions

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In rainfed lowland rice-growing areas with impeded drainage, water may stagnate at depths above 25 cm for much of the growing season. Field experiments were conducted under medium deep conditions at IRRI 1983-

Yields of promising rainfed lowland rices and check cultivars grown under medium deepwater conditions (25-50 cm water depth). IRRI, 1983-85.

Designation	Duration ^a (d)	Height ^a (cm)	Lodging ^a score	Yield (t/ha)			Grand mean yield (t/ha)
				1983	1984	1985	
IR13149-71-3-2-3	127	123	3.2	2.7	2.9	4.4	3.3
IR24705-11-3-2-3-3	137	123	2.8	1.9	3.0	4.5	3.2
IR26760-27-1-3-2-1	141	131	4.3	2.1	2.6	4.2	3.0
IR26760-76-2-1-2-3	133	128	3.5	2.0	2.5	4.3	2.9
IR19382-42-3-3-2	136	134	2.3	2.4	2.3	4.0	2.9
IR9217-58-2-2	126	127	3.3	2.6	2.5	3.3	2.8
IR54	120	119	5.3	2.4	2.0	2.7	2.4
IR42	129	113	2.7	1.9	1.8	3.2	2.3
Mahsuri	132	152	7.0	0.6	1.4	1.3	1.1
LSD (0.05)				0.8	0.6	0.9	

^aDuration, height, and lodging score (SES scale) are means from the 3 yr.